

Management and productivity of farmers' boro rice

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In Bangladesh, spring (boro) rice is grown where surface or irrigation water is available. The crop is transplanted during the dry winter months of December and January and harvested during the hot spring months of April and May. In the river floodplains, irrigation is lifted by low lift pumps or by traditional swing baskets. In shallow terraced valleys and depressions with natural standing water, rice is sometimes double-transplanted as water recedes or is irrigated by low lift pumps and traditional irrigation equipment. In some

highland areas without surface water, cultivation is dependent on tube well irrigation.

In recent years, as more pumps became available for irrigation in the dry season, a shift in rice cropping patterns has been observed, from the more risky, low-yielding deepwater aus rices in winter to the high-yielding boro varieties in spring.

A crop-cut study during 1975-76 boro assessed management level and yield of five improved varieties and two local varieties grown in the BRRRI project area. Five-square-meter areas were harvested from 178 fields in 19 villages. The crop was threshed, cleaned, weighed, and moisture determined. Yield was converted to tons per hectare at 14% moisture. Information on fertilizer and insect and weed control was collected from farmers.

Average NPK application was greater

on improved varieties than on local varieties. Farmers growing improved varieties used almost twice the amount of nitrogen as those growing local varieties. Most nitrogen fertilizer was applied in 3 splits: 30-40 kg as basal, 40 kg as first topdressing, and 30 kg as second topdressing.

Improved varieties outyielded local varieties (see table). Highest daily production was from IR9 and BR3. Generally, yields of improved varieties are higher in the boro season than in other seasons because of high solar radiation and low disease and pest incidence.

Most farmers did relatively good weeding, as is reflected by the weed control index at the time of harvest. About 60-70% used insecticides. Straw dry weight of IR9, Pajam, and Lathisail differed significantly from that of other varieties. ■

Management level and average yield of boro rice grown in BRRRI Project area, Bangladesh, 1975-76.

Variety		Average rate of fertilizer N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O (kg/ha)	Weed control index ^a	Farmers using pesticides (%)	Straw dry weight ^b (t/ha)	Average yield ^b (t/ha)	Yield range (t/ha)	Estimated yield/day ^b (kg/ha)
IR9	8	97-99-26	2.50	67	3.8 a	4.0 a	2.5-5.9	39.8 a
Pajam	18	U4-63-27	2.20	40	3.0 a	4.4 a	2.9-6.5	34.8 a
UR3	2	88-96-43	3.00	100	2.8 b	4.1 a	3.9-4.3	39.2 a
IR8	111	88-62-37	3.07	55	2.9 b	4.1 a	1.6-7.2	32.9 a
Chandina	14	85-68-48	3.10	64	2.1 c	3.6 a	9.8-5.6	37.7 a
Muktahar	18	43-44-30	2.83	53	2.8 b	2.1 b	1.2-3.2	20.6 b
Lathisail	7	43-30-26	2.00	0	3.5 a	1.9 b	0.7-3.3	17.6 b

^a1 = excellent control, 5 = poor control. ^bIn a column, figures followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Machinery development and testing

Economic use of Japanese walking-type rice transplanters in Egypt

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Two rice transplanting machines were used in a 1979-81 study comparing mechanical and hand planting. The two-row Mitsubishi MP 206 and the four-row Yanmar YP 400 transplanters are walking, handdriven types. The Japanese method of raising the seedlings in a wooden frame 370 × 114 cm containing

Table 1. Comparative yield components with direct seeding, hand, and mechanical transplanting at kafr El-Seikh, Egypt, 1979.

Planting method	Seeding rates (kg/ha)	Plant ht at harvest (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)	Branches (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Direct seeding</i>							
Broadcasting	95-144	131.6	488.9	22.01	7.60	24.0	7.08
Drilled	95-144	137.4	418.2	23.65	11.50	24.0	9.2
<i>Transplanting</i>							
Farmer by hand ^a	95-144	129.5	324	22.05	9.9	24.2	6.2
Recommended by hand ^b	95-144	139.3	380.4	23.28	11.12	26.6	9.1
Mechanical ^c	36-48	140.6	503.4	25.14	12.5	25.0	10.1

^aThe distance of farmer hand transplanting between hills and rows is not fixed. ^bRecommended hand transplanting density = 20 × 20 cm. ^cMechanical transplanting density: MP 206 = 30 × 15 cm. YP 400 = 30 × 14 cm.

3 seedling mats measuring $360 \times 28 \times 3$ cm was used. Seedling mats obtained from each frame are enough to transplant 1,000 m².

Seeds of cultivar Giza 172 were soaked at the same time for direct seeding, hand transplanting, and mechanical transplanting treatments. Seedling age was 2.5-3.5 leaves for mechanical transplanting, 5-6 leaves for recommended transplanting, and 6-7 leaves for traditional farmer transplanting. Water depth at transplanting was 3-4 cm for mechanical transplanting and 5-10 cm for hand transplanting.

Mechanical transplanting gave higher brown rice yields than traditional methods (Table 1). The high yield with

Table 2. Cost for hand and machine transplanting and yield of brown rice of Giza 172, kafr El Seikh, Egypt, 1980.

Planting method	(Cost ^a (\$/ha))				Brown rice yield (t/ha)
	Initial cost to transplant 1 ha	Wooden frame	Seed	Total	
Hand transplanting	102.87		12.00	116.91	4.3
Machine transplanting (MP 206)	44.00	2.77	5.14	52.00	11.8
Av yield in Egypt					6.2

^aConverted at the rate of US\$1 — Egyptian pound 0.70

mechanical transplanting could be explained by the high number of panicles per unit area and by larger, heavy panicles and vigorous growth. Vigorous young seedlings, a larger number of hills per unit area, and early machine transplanting caused the high yields in 1970

and 1980. The use in 1981 of rice transplanter YP 400 with its autohydraulic system increased efficiency.

The total cost of hand transplanting was 2.5 times greater than the cost of machine transplanting (Table 2). ■

Announcement

First IRRI trustee president dies

The first president of IRRI's Board of Trustees, Dr. J. George Harrar, died 18 April 1982 at his home in Scarsdale, New York, USA. DR. Harrar, a biologist, was often credited with initiating the increase in agricultural productivity in developing nations that is known as the "green revolution."

The former president of the Rockefeller Foundation was one of five original members of the corporation that established IRRI in 1960-61. The international agricultural research centers now encompass a global network of 13 institutions that in 1981 received more than \$120 million from nations and agencies committed to international agricultural development.

The recipient of some 30 honorary degrees from universities in the United States and abroad, Dr. Harrar also was decorated by the governments of Mexico, Thailand, Colombia, and Chile. He was the author of some 60 professional papers in phytopathology and mycology and published 50 articles on world agriculture, food and population, higher education, environmental quality, and nutrition. He also authored or co-

authored 3 books, the last *Strategy for the Coquest of Hunger* in 1967.

With Rockefeller Foundation from 1943 until his retirement in 1972, He was a leader in the application of scientific methods to raise the quality and quantity of food. Under his administration as president and trustee of the Foundation, almost \$400 million was appropriated to carry forward projects to increase productivity of basic food crops, to reduce

population growth rates, to develop universities, to bring about equality of opportunity for minorities, to foster the performing arts, and to improve the quality of the environment.

In 1980, the original scholar and training building complex at IRRI was dedicated as J. George Harrar Hall in honor of his contribution to the Institute. ■

J. George Harrar Hall, IRRI's original scholar and training building complex dedicated in 1980. Inset, Dr. Harrar during his tenure as the first president of IRRI's Board of Trustees.